

Empirical characterization of in-vehicle propagation at different frequency bands

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Abstract—This paper presents an empirical characterization of in-vehicle radio wave propagation across multiple frequency bands, including FR1, FR2, FR3, and sub-THz. Measurements are conducted on three different car types in both line-of-sight and obstructed-line-of-sight conditions. Key propagation metrics, such as path loss, delay spread and transmission loss through different car components are evaluated in order to analyze radio channel characteristics for the purpose of designing future 6G in-vehicle sub-networks. The obtained results highlight significant differences in signal attenuation, time dispersion and scattering effects between the analyzed frequency bands, especially in obstructed line-of-sight scenarios when the wireless nodes are located in the vicinity of vehicle components like seats and under-seat areas.

Index Terms—in-vehicle propagation, radio channel characterization, propagation measurements.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the 2030 decade, 6G communications will bring a new era in which billions of things, humans, vehicles, robots and drones will be connected together and generate a huge amount of digital information [1]. On that perspective, there is a lot of ongoing research on the design of key technology components to enable the deployment of in-X wireless subnetworks, i.e., short-range, low-power radio cells, across a wide range of vertical and consumer entities, such as robots, vehicles, manufacturing modules, etc., as well as their connection to a larger 6G “network of networks.” [2].

In-vehicle sub-networks will be an important part of the 6G ecosystem: they are necessary to have vehicles connected to the network, and equipped with advanced features such as autonomous driving, that request to exchange data between several components such as sensors, actuators, control units, and computing systems. Due to the critical timing, reliability, and safety requirements of automotive functions and services, in-vehicle communications nowadays mostly rely on cable links. Replacing cables with in-vehicle wireless links will facilitate the evolution of in-vehicle networks and enable the incorporation of new functionalities through the vehicle’s lifespan, in addition to reducing the vehicle’s weight and reducing fuel or battery consumption.

Currently, there are only a few studies related to in-vehicle sub-networks: some use cases are presented and analyzed in the EU SNS JU flagship project HEXA-X-II [3], while extensive research on this topic has recently been initiated in the EU SNS JU project 6G-SHINE [4].

In order to make the communication between wireless nodes in a vehicle feasible, it is necessary to investigate the characteristics of radio propagation in short-range and cluttered environments such as the different zones, spaces and technology components inside a car. Moreover, as 6G will address several new frequency bands such as the mid-band 7-24 GHz (also known as FR3 band), the higher mm-waves band and the sub-THz band, it is important to assess in-vehicle radio propagation on a wide range of frequencies.

Therefore, the goal of this work is to present a multi-band measurement campaign carried out in the framework of the 6G-SHINE project at University of Bologna, Italy, and Aalborg University, Denmark, on three different car types and in typical configurations of the wireless nodes, i.e. Line-of-sight (LoS) and Obstructed-line-of-sight (OLoS). The results of this measurement campaign have been partly reported in [5], where the focus of the analysis was on the identification of the major multipath components (MPC), through the comparison of the Power-angle-delay profiles at different frequency bands.

In the present work, we aim to analyze in detail some key parameters related to the radio channel characteristics such as Path loss (PL), Power-delay profile (PDP), Delay spread (DS), and signal penetration loss through different car items.

The present paper is organized as follows: in Section II, the measurement equipment and setups and the propagation environments are described. Section III explains the measurement post-processing procedure and how the channel parameters are extracted from the measured channel impulse responses. In Section IV preliminary results are presented, and in Section V conclusions are drawn.

II. MEASUREMENTS EQUIPMENT AND SETUPS

In the measurement campaign, we consider different measurement setups, frequency bands, and vehicle types. In particular, the vehicles tested in the measurement campaign are a Mercedes Benz 200d, a Tesla Model Y, and a Seat Leon. The measurement campaign was split into two parts: the first one was conducted at the Cesena Campus of the University of Bologna and mainly dealt with OLoS measurements at FR3 frequencies (8 – 12 GHz) and sub-THz frequencies, specifically the D-band (110–170 GHz); the second took place at Aalborg University and focused on LoS measurements at 4 – 6.5 GHz, 25 – 27.5 GHz and 99 – 101.5 GHz. In both cases, the measurement scenario consists of a transmitting

Fig. 1. Pictures of various in-vehicle OLoS scenarios. The distance between Tx and Rx is 0.5 m for scenario 1, 0.45 m for scenario 2 and scenario 3 at D-Band frequencies. At X-Band frequencies, the distance between Tx and Rx is 1.4 m for scenario 1, while for scenarios 2 and 3 the distance is 1.1 m.

Fig. 2. Pictures of the various in-vehicle LoS scenarios. The link distances are the following: scenario A 0.91 m, scenario B 1.62 m, and scenario C 0.88 m.

antenna (Tx), a receiving antenna (Rx) located inside the vehicle and a Vector network analyzer (VNA) used to record the measurements.

A. Measurements Equipment

For the part of the measurements conducted at the Cesena Campus Keysight's PNA-X Network Analyzer N5242B (10 MHz - 26.5 GHz) was used. This VNA was additionally equipped with VDI extender modules WR6.5-VNAX that perform down and up-conversion, in order to extend the frequency range to the D-band. For the measurement campaign executed at Aalborg University, the VNA (R&S ZNA 43) was used, with VDI extender modules (WR10-VNAX) integrated for Sub-THz band (99 – 101.5 GHz) measurements. The chosen antenna setup for the in-vehicle OLoS scenario consists of standard gain horn antennas with an average gain of 16 – 18 dBi (ARRA X820) in the FR3 band, and VDI conical horn antennas WR 6.5 with a gain of 20 – 22 dBi in the D-band. On the other hand, for the in-vehicle LoS scenario, wideband omnidirectional antennas have been used, with a gain in the range of 1 – 3 dBi.

B. Measurement setups

We consider different LoS and OLoS scenarios for the characterization of in-vehicle propagation. The different setups for OLoS scenarios are shown in Fig. 1. In Scenario 1, both the Tx and Rx are placed on the seats, horizontally aligned, and oriented towards the seat backrest that separates them. In Scenario 2, the Tx and Rx are placed on the ground and directed towards each other. Scenario 3 mirrors Scenario 2, but with the receiver tilted 90° on the horizontal plane, facing inward towards the interior of the car. Fig. 2 shows the

setups of the measurement in the LoS scenarios inside the car Mercedes Benz 200d. Here the Tx antenna was placed on the dashboard of the car, while the Rx antenna was placed on the side door, back seat and front seat for scenarios A, B and C, respectively.

III. MEASUREMENT POST-PROCESSING

A. Power Delay Profile and Associated Parameters

In order to extract PDPs, the Channel frequency response (CFR) $H(f)$, obtained through the VNA is preliminarily filtered using a Hanning window $W(f)$. The Hanning window allows to minimize of discontinuities at the boundaries of the sampled signal and reduces aliasing. Note that the whole measured frequency bands could be preliminarily divided into sub-bands before obtaining multipath components in the time domain, to better analyze the channel characteristics at different sub-bands. The Channel impulse response (CIR) is then obtained by

$$h(\tau) = \mathcal{F}^{-1}[W(f) \cdot H(f)], \quad (1)$$

where \mathcal{F}^{-1} denotes the inverse Fourier transform. The PDP is then given by [6]

$$P(\tau) = |h(\tau)|^2. \quad (2)$$

The PL is calculated considering all the propagation paths in the PDP. These paths are identified by selecting a proper noise threshold and then conducting 1-D local maxima search on the PDP. Assuming that we have identified N paths in total, the PL is given by

$$PL[dB] = -10 \log_{10} \left(\sum_{n=1}^N \frac{P_n}{G_{Tx} \cdot G_{Rx}} \right), \quad (3)$$

where P_n is the value of the PDP for the n -th identified path. G_{Tx} and G_{Rx} represent the antenna gain of the Tx and Rx antennas, respectively.

Root-mean square (RMS) Delay spread (DS) is a metric for evaluating the time dispersion of the Multipath components (MPCs). We calculate the DS based on the identified paths from the PDP, i.e. [6],

$$\tau_{rms} = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{n=1}^N (\tau_n - \bar{\tau})^2 P_n}{\sum_{n=1}^N P_n}}, \quad (4)$$

where τ_n is the relative time delay between the first path and the n -th path, while the average delay $\bar{\tau}$ is derived by

$$\bar{\tau} = \frac{\sum_{n=1}^N \tau_n P_n}{\sum_{n=1}^N P_n}. \quad (5)$$

B. Transmission Loss

For the transmission loss analysis, the transmitter and receiver were horizontally aligned and directed towards the obstructing object. The link distance was chosen to be small enough to ensure that the footprint of the antenna's main lobe falls entirely on the object under test, and is sufficiently far from the edges of the object. The setups employed for the transmission loss measurements are only scenario 1 and scenario 2, shown in Fig. 1.

Since the entire antenna footprint falls within the area of interest, we are certain that the first CIR peak is caused by the OLoS path, and not by diffractions on the edges of the object. Therefore we used a method based on the time-gating technique, where an appropriate time window is applied to isolate the main peak of the CIR. Once the corresponding power is obtained, we subtract this value (in dB units) from the received power of the LoS path extracted from the calibration measurement, to calculate the desired attenuation.

IV. RESULTS

In the following, preliminary results are shown for different frequency bands and car types. In particular, we consider the FR1, FR2, FR3, and sub-THz (99 – 101.5 GHz and D-band) frequency ranges. The vehicles of interest are the Mercedes Benz B200d, Tesla Model Y, and Seat Leon.

A. Transmission Loss of different car components

To achieve a more comprehensive analysis of signal attenuation we compared the penetration loss values at both lower frequencies, selecting the mid-band (FR3), and the higher sub-THz frequencies (D-Band). The transmission loss values were examined for different in-vehicle OLoS scenarios with two different obstructing obstacles: the seat backrest and the area under the seat, where plastic parts partially obstruct the LoS path. The analysis of signal attenuation was conducted in two cars: Tesla Model Y and Seat Leon.

Fig. 3, reports the penetration loss values as a function of frequency over the range of 110 – 170 GHz and pertain to the signal attenuation considering both the obstruction caused by the seat backrest and by the environment under the seat.

TABLE I
AVERAGE PENETRATION LOSS VALUES AND STANDARD DEVIATIONS AT D-BAND FREQUENCIES IN AN IN-VEHICLE OLoS SCENARIO WITH DIFFERENT OBSTRUCTING OBSTACLES.

Obstruction obstacles	110-170 GHz	
	Mean L [dB]	σ [dB]
Seat backrest Tesla Model Y	12.65 dB	1.86 dB
Seat backrest Seat Leon	8.23 dB	1.42 dB
Environment under the seat	5.16 dB	1.17 dB

The penetration loss curves as a function of frequency were obtained using the time-gating method outlined in sub-section III-B, and by dividing the whole measured band into 10 sub-bands. The solid red curve shows the signal attenuation in a scenario where the line of sight is obstructed by the environment under the seat of the Tesla Model Y. It is noteworthy that for the D-Band the environment under the seat can also contribute to a non-negligible transmission loss, with values around 2 dB at frequencies of 113 GHz, reaching up to 6.3 dB at 167 GHz.

The solid blue and green curves provide the penetration loss values where the LoS between antennas is obstructed by a seat backrest for the different car models. From these two curves, it emerges that the seat backrest of the Tesla Model Y exhibits greater attenuation compared to that of the Seat Leon. Specifically, in the case of the Seat Leon, the penetration loss values range from a minimum of 7.18 dB at 113 GHz to a maximum of 10.84 dB at 167 GHz. The Tesla Model Y, instead, shows values ranging from a minimum of 9.83 dB to a maximum of 15.66 dB. This difference in attenuation values between the seat backrests of the two vehicles is due to their materials and thickness. Table I summarizes the average penetration loss and standard deviation for different obstructing obstacles and for different vehicles. For the penetration loss at 8 – 12 GHz, the results show that the obstruction caused by the seat backrest and by the environment under the seats are negligible, approximately 0.5 – 1 dB and 1 – 1.5 dB respectively.

B. Path loss and Delay Spread analysis

The results of the PL and RMS Delay Spread analysis pertain to the in-vehicle OLoS and LoS scenarios, shown in Fig. 1 - 2, across different frequencies.

Fig. 4 shows the PDPs for scenario A. From the PDPs, it can be observed that the main path has a delay of approximately 3 ns, which corresponds to the distance between Rx and Tx. Note that the antenna gains are de-embedded in the PDP results. Typically, the MPCs in these scenarios are caused by the reflections from surrounding windows, roof and chairs in the passenger cabin. Strong MPCs can be observed in both the sub-6 GHz and mmWave bands whereas the LoS path tends to dominate the channels in the sub-THz bands. Comparing the PDP results for different frequency bands, the LoS path can be identified in all the frequency bands and major MPCs can be recognized in both the low and mmWave frequencies.

TABLE II

TABLE OF RMS DELAY SPREAD, PATH LOSS, AND IFSP L VALUES FOR DIFFERENT IN-VEHICLE LOS SCENARIOS, SHOWN IN FIG.2, ACROSS VARIOUS FREQUENCY RANGES.

scenario	In-vehicle LoS scenarios								
	4 - 6.5 GHz			25 - 27.5 GHz			99 - 101.5 GHz		
	τ_{rms} (ns)	PL (dB)	IFSP L (dB)	τ_{rms} (ns)	PL (dB)	IFSP L (dB)	τ_{rms} (ns)	PL (dB)	IFSP L (dB)
scenario A	2.51	42.52	46.03	3.3	55.76	60.01	0.57	70	71.64
scenario B	9.74	43.66	51.04	2.54	61.31	65.01	1.76	76.03	76.65
scenario C	5.46	40.51	45.73	2.53	55.02	59.71	0.8	69.12	71.35

TABLE III

TABLE OF RMS DELAY SPREAD, PL, AND IFSP L VALUES FOR DIFFERENT IN-VEHICLE OLoS SCENARIOS, SHOWN IN FIG.1, AT D-BAND AND X-BAND FOR EACH SUB-BAND. NOTE: THE SYMBOL '-' INDICATES THAT THE IFSP L VALUES FOR SCENARIO 3 ARE IDENTICAL TO THOSE FOR SCENARIO 2.

In-vehicle OLoS scenarios D-Band frequencies									
sub-Band	scenario 1			scenario 2			scenario 3		
	τ_{rms} (ns)	PL (dB)	IFSP L (dB)	τ_{rms} (ns)	PL (dB)	IFSP L (dB)	τ_{rms} (ns)	PL (dB)	IFSP L (dB)
110 – 116 GHz	0.17	83.99	67.48	0.27	74.29	66.57	5.67	107.48	-
116 – 122 GHz	0.14	84.20	67.93	0.17	75.51	67.02	3.30	106.93	-
122 – 128 GHz	0.12	84.34	68.36	0.20	74.59	67.44	4.17	109.96	-
128 – 134 GHz	0.10	86.69	68.77	0.14	74.74	67.85	3.41	109.30	-
134 – 140 GHz	0.15	85.18	69.16	0.17	76.84	68.24	4.17	110.09	-
140 – 146 GHz	0.18	85.42	69.53	0.15	76.05	68.61	4.43	108.89	-
146 – 152 GHz	0.20	87.49	69.88	0.29	75.45	68.97	5.55	111.07	-
152 – 158 GHz	0.11	85.51	70.23	0.37	74.81	69.31	3.93	111.18	-
158 – 164 GHz	0.26	87.43	70.55	0.44	75.31	69.64	6.03	111.35	-
164 – 170 GHz	0.27	89.12	70.87	0.41	76.09	69.96	8.18	111.89	-

In-vehicle OLoS scenarios X-Band frequencies									
sub-Band	scenario 1			scenario 2			scenario 3		
	τ_{rms} (ns)	PL (dB)	IFSP L (dB)	τ_{rms} (ns)	PL (dB)	IFSP L (dB)	τ_{rms} (ns)	PL (dB)	IFSP L (dB)
8 – 10 GHz	0.55	49.9	54.55	1.14	52.5	52.35	7.6	72.17	-
10 – 12 GHz	0.4	50.01	56.19	1.09	54.9	54.1	6.8	75.51	-

Fig. 3. Penetration loss values at D-Band frequencies where obstructing obstacles are: seat backrest of the Tesla Model Y, seat backrest of the Seat Leon, and the environment under the seats of the Tesla Model Y.

Fig. 4. PDPs at different band of frequencies (4 – 6.5 GHz, 25 – 27.5 GHz, 99 – 101.5 GHz) for scenario A, shown in Fig.2.

Tables II and III summarize the RMS delay spread, PL and Isotropic Free space path loss (IFSP L) results for LoS scenarios A, B, C and for OLoS scenario 1, 2 and 3, and for all the frequency bands. In the tables, the FR3 band and the D-band are divided into 2 and 10 sub-bands, respectively.

Note that the IFSP L is also provided as a reference value, which is derived by

$$IFSP L = 20 \log_{10} \left(\frac{4\pi d f_c}{c} \right), \quad (6)$$

where f_c is the centre frequency of the considered frequency sub-band and d is the link distance. Subsequently, the results will be discussed for each frequency, distinguishing between LoS and OLoS scenarios.

1) LoS scenarios:

4 – 6.5 GHz: The calculated PL is, on average, around 5 dB lower than the corresponding IFSP L for the three scenarios and the difference reaches 7.38 dB for scenario B. With also the highest DS, i.e., 9.74 ns, it can be inferred that more

MPCs with relatively high powers are identified in scenario B compared to the other two scenarios. In most cases, the DS calculated at 4 – 6.5 GHz is larger than the other two bands due to the smaller propagation and scattering losses. The car, with all the windows closed, is a small and enclosed space, containing complicated structures inside, which causes significant MPC effects for low-frequency bands.

25 – 27.5 GHz: The PL is, on average, 4 dB lower than the corresponding IFSPL. Although the mmWave bands generally exhibit higher PL compared to lower frequency bands, most of the MPCs can still be detected, significantly influencing the observed channels. The DS values in the mmWave bands are consistently lower than those in the 4–6.5 GHz range, but higher than those in the 99 – 101.5 GHz range. Overall, the channel characteristics in the mmWave bands resemble those of the lower frequency bands more than those of the sub-THz bands.

99 – 101.5 GHz: The calculated PL in this band is much closer to the IFSPL compared to the other two bands, with a maximum difference of 2.23 dB in scenario C. As mentioned earlier, the LoS path has significantly more power than the other MPCs, which means the scattering paths have less impact on the channels at sub-THz frequencies. Scenario B shows the largest DS among the three scenarios due to a greater link distance. However, its DS values are the smallest across the three frequency bands because of the extremely high propagation and scattering losses in sub-THz bands.

2) OLoS scenarios:

8 – 12 GHz: The difference between PL and IFSPL is of few dBs in Scenario 1, and almost negligible in Scenario 2. Therefore, communication in the FR3 band is not much affected by attenuation from the internal car furniture. In scenario 3, both the PL and DS values are higher compared to the other two scenarios. This can be attributed to the rotation of the receiver towards the passenger side.

110 – 170 GHz: It is observed that the PL values for all three OLoS scenarios are significantly higher than the corresponding IFSPL values.

This increase in the PL values can be attributed to the obstructed line-of-sight condition, whereas penetration losses through the car furniture are much higher at sub-THz frequencies. In scenario 2, the PL values are lower because the cluttering under the seat obstructs the LoS to a lower extent than the seat backrest. However, these values are significantly higher than the IFSPL values, differently to what happens in the FR3 band, meaning that at sub-THz frequencies even partial obstructions or cluttering effects can cause a drop of the signal intensity of several dBs. Scenario 3 exhibits even higher PL values, as the directional receiving antenna is rotated of 90°, i.e. oriented towards the passenger side. In this case, also DS values increase by an order of magnitude with respect to Scenarios 1 and 2, due to a greater attenuation of the LoS path. At the same time, communication is still possible through reflected paths on the car sidewalls and furniture, as in the PDP there are several MPCs well above

the noise threshold. In addition, as it can be inferred from Table III, in the D-Band there is a slight increase in delay spread with the frequency in all the OLoS scenarios, as the penetration loss that affects the direct path attenuates more rapidly with the frequency compared to the reflected paths from the surrounding environment.

V. CONCLUSION

An extensive measurement campaign in an in-vehicle environment has been carried out, covering LoS and OLoS scenarios and a wide range of frequency bands, from below-6GHz frequencies to sub-THz frequencies. Measurements in LoS scenarios indicate that MPCs significantly impact the channel characteristics at frequencies below the sub-THz bands. In contrast, the LoS path dominates at sub-THz frequencies. Consequently, higher PL and larger RMS delay spread values are observed in the lower and mm-Wave bands compared to the sub-THz bands. In OLoS measurements at D-Band frequencies, significant transmission losses due to obstruction from the seat backrest and the environment under the seat are observed, while the same losses are almost negligible at FR3 frequencies. Moreover, an opposite trend of the delay spread is observed compared to LoS measurements, as DS tend to increase with the frequency due to the higher penetration losses that significantly reduce the intensity of the obstructed direct path.

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